

A SOLUTION TO THE NEGATIVE ENERGY OF THE UNIVERSE BY CONSIDERING UNIVERSE AS A WAVE FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this paper is to consider the universe as a superposition of the incident and reflecting standing wave, taking any frequency as per our liking and then from that we will derive the PLANK-EINSTEIN RELATION through Schrödinger's Equation and Klein-Gordon Equation and then after computing the relation as $E = \hbar\omega$, we will use the negative formulation of this same energy as $E = -\hbar\omega$, and then relating the Positive energy with the negative energy with a series of mathematical calculations of using quantum theory and special relativity, we will be able to derive a universal fact that positive energy is equal to negative energy and as they are equal, so the difference between the above energy spectrum is zero which helps us to conclude that the energy is always conserved in this universe meaning there is neither excess, nor less energy as compared with both the negative values of the energy and then we will assume an orthogonal coordinate equation of the XYZ-Plane to formulate a 3D Graph thereby concluding what we started as the universe with the wavefunction of a specified frequency. The paper aims to achieve the conclusion by taking the antinodes and nodes of a standing wave as the Positive Energy and Negative Energy or vice versa, as the pattern doesn't matter, what matters is that the total difference between them is zero and thereby energy is conserved.

THEORY AND INTERPRETATION

Let us take any specific frequency and here we have taken 2.5 Hertz and then computing the 1-Dimensional Graph, it looks like...

Time - 1 second, Frequency - 2.5 Hertz, Oscillations - 2 and 1/2

Here we can see a 1-Dimensional standing wave. We will consider both the incident and reflecting nature of this wave as an exponential wavefunctions...

$$Ae^{i(kx - \omega t)}$$

$$Ae^{i(kx + \omega t)}$$

Combining this two we get,

$$2A(e^{i(kx - \omega t)} + e^{i(kx + \omega t)})$$

Now we will expand it in the form $e^{i\theta} = \cos \theta + i \sin \theta$...

$$2A\{\cos(kx - \omega t) + i \sin(kx - \omega t) + \cos(kx + \omega t) + i \sin(kx + \omega t)\}$$

Expanding it furthermore,

$$2A\{(\cos kx \cos \omega t) + (\sin kx \sin \omega t) + i(\sin kx \cos \omega t) - i(\cos kx \sin \omega t) + (\cos kx \cos \omega t) - (\sin kx \sin \omega t) + i(\sin kx \cos \omega t) + i(\cos kx \sin \omega t)\}$$

Then simplifying it,

$$2A\{2(\cos kx \cos \omega t) + 2i(\sin kx \cos \omega t)\}$$

Now, we will introduce a 1-Dimensional wavefunction as $\Psi_{(x)}$,

$$\Psi_{(x)} = 4A\{(\cos kx \cos \omega t) + i(\sin kx \cos \omega t)\}$$

Taking Partial Derivative on both sides,

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \Psi_{(x)} = 4A \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} (\cos kx \cos \omega t) + 4Ai \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} (\sin kx \cos \omega t)$$

Which equals to...

$$-4Ak^2 (\text{Cos } kx \text{ Cos } \omega t) - 4Aik^2 (\text{Sin } kx \text{ Cos } \omega t)$$

Therefore, we get the following equation,

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \Psi(x) = -4Ak^2 \{ (\text{Cos } kx \text{ Cos } \omega t) + i (\text{Sin } kx \text{ Cos } \omega t) \}$$

Now, its time to introduce the famous Schrodinger's Equation,

$$E\Psi(x) = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \Psi(x) + V(x)\Psi(x)$$

Or,

$$(E - V)\Psi(x) = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \Psi(x)$$

Putting the values of $\Psi(x)$ in LHS and $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \Psi(x)$ in RHS, we get,

$$(E - V) [4A \{ (\text{Cos } kx \text{ Cos } \omega t) + i (\text{Sin } kx \text{ Cos } \omega t) \}] = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} [-4Ak^2 \{ (\text{Cos } kx \text{ Cos } \omega t) + i (\text{Sin } kx \text{ Cos } \omega t) \}]$$

We know the Quantum Mechanical analogue of momentum, that is $P = \hbar k$, after cancellation in both sides we get,

$$E - V = \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m} = \frac{P^2}{2m}$$

Now formulating the KLEIN-GORDON Equations², we will get,

$$\mathbf{P} = -i\hbar\nabla \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{E} = i\hbar \partial/\partial t$$

The Schrodinger equation can't be explained on the basis of relativity, therefore, it is quite natural to use the identity of special relativity to describe energy:

$$E = \sqrt{P^2c^2 + m^2c^4}$$

Now, inserting the Quantum mechanical operators for Energy & Momentum yields the equation as...

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Psi(x)) = \sqrt{((-i\hbar\nabla)^2c^2 + m^2c^4)} (\Psi(x))$$

KLEIN-GORDON² Equation takes place....

$$\mathbf{E}^2 = \mathbf{P}^2c^2 + m^2c^4$$

After Quantization the equation becomes,

$$(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t})^2 (\Psi(x)) = (-i\hbar\nabla)^2c^2 + m^2c^4 (\Psi(x))$$

Or,

$$-h^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi(x) = -h^2c^2 \nabla^2 \Psi(x) + m^2c^4 \Psi(x)$$

Dividing both sides by \hbar^2c^2 ,

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi(x) - \nabla^2 \Psi(x) + \frac{m^2c^2 \Psi(x)}{h^2} = 0$$

Putting the values of $\Psi_{(x)}$ in LHS and $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi_{(x)}$ in the above equation,

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \{-4A\omega^2 \cos kx \cos \omega t - 4A\omega^2 i \sin kx \cos \omega t\} + 4Ak^2 \{(\cos kx \cos \omega t) + i (\sin kx \cos \omega t)\} + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} 4A \{(\cos kx \cos \omega t) + i (\sin kx \cos \omega t)\} = 0$$

This becomes,

$$-4A\omega^2 \frac{1}{c^2} \{(\cos kx \cos \omega t) + i (\sin kx \cos \omega t)\} + 4Ak^2 \{(\cos kx \cos \omega t) + i (\sin kx \cos \omega t)\} + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} 4A \{(\cos kx \cos \omega t) + i (\sin kx \cos \omega t)\} = 0$$

After cancellation on both sides, this reduces to...

$$4Ak^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} 4A = 4A\omega^2 \frac{1}{c^2}$$

$$k^2 \hbar^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4 = \hbar^2 \omega^2$$

$$p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4 = \hbar^2 \omega^2$$

$$E^2 = \hbar^2 \omega^2$$

$$E = \hbar \omega$$

Finally, we get the desired relation $E = \hbar \omega$

Now deriving the desired result of Positive Energy as $E = \hbar \omega$, we will take the negative energy as $E = -\hbar \omega$ and then perform the following operations as follows...

So, coming back to our old friend, we will consider the Wave function equation as $2A \sin(Kx) \cos(\omega t)$.

For Antinodes the value of $\sin(kx) = +/- 1 \Rightarrow \pi/2, 3\pi/2, \dots$

For Node the value of $\sin(Kx) = 0 \Rightarrow 0, \pi$

Taking the total energy as $E^2 = \hbar^2 \omega^2 - \hbar^2 \omega^2$ where $[\hbar^2 \omega^2]$ is the Anti-Node & $[-\hbar^2 \omega^2]$ is the node]

Substituting Antinode for e_1 & Node for e_2 , we will form 2 Equations with e & e' .

$$e = e_1 - e_2$$

$$e' = e_1 - e_2$$

The Matrix Representation of the above Equation is...

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \pi/2 & -0 \\ 3\pi/2 & -\pi \end{pmatrix} \begin{matrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{matrix} = \begin{matrix} e \\ e' \end{matrix}$$

Now, to make *EIGENVALUES & EIGENVECTORS*, we will take I as a unitary Matrix and Multiplied it with Λ .

$$\Lambda I = \Lambda \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda & 0 \\ 0 & \Lambda \end{pmatrix}$$

$$A - \Lambda I = \begin{pmatrix} \pi/2 & -0 \\ 3\pi/2 & -\pi \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda & 0 \\ 0 & \Lambda \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \pi/2 - \Lambda & 0 \\ 3\pi/2 & -\pi - \Lambda \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\text{Determinant } [A - \Lambda I] = (\pi/2 - \Lambda) * (-\pi - \Lambda) - (3\pi/2) * (0) = -\pi^2/2 - \pi\Lambda/2 + \pi\Lambda + \Lambda^2$$

Putting the Value of $\pi = 180$

$$-16200 - 90\Lambda + 180\Lambda + \Lambda^2$$

$$\Lambda^2 + 90\Lambda - 16200$$

$$\Lambda^2 + 180\Lambda - 90\Lambda - 16200$$

$$(\Lambda + 180)(\Lambda - 90)$$

$$\Lambda = -180$$

$$\Lambda = 90$$

[These are the respective EIGENVALUES but we will take only the second value that is 90]

$$A - \Lambda I = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\pi}{2} - \Lambda & 0 \\ 3\pi/2 & -\pi - \Lambda \end{pmatrix}$$

Substituting with the value of $\Lambda = 90$ & writing $\pi = 180$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{180}{2} - 90 & 0 \\ 3 * 180/2 & -180 - 90 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 270 & -270 \end{pmatrix}$$

Now, we will do the *ROW REDUCTION* as follows...

1. Interchanging the first & second row $\begin{pmatrix} 270 & -270 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
2. Multiply first row by $1/270$ as $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$

$$\text{Let } B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$B\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{0}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Therefore,

$$1 * X_1 - 1 * X_2 = 0 \Rightarrow X_1 = X_2$$

Therefore if $X_1 = 1$ & $X_2 = 1$ then the equations satisfies and they are the *EIGENVECTORS*.

[PROOF]

$$\begin{pmatrix} \pi/2 & -0 \\ 3\pi/2 & -\pi \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 90 * \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

FURTHER EXTRAPOLATION YIELDS THAT THE TOTAL ENERGY OF THE UNIVERSE IS ZERO. THIS MEANS THAT SOME POSITIVE POTENTIAL MUST BE ACTING ON SOME NEGATIVE POTENTIAL TO GET THE NEUTRAL ENERGY. THAT MEANS, NODES & ANTINODES ARE BEHAVING AS OPPOSITE ENERGIES. IF WE PREDICT OUR UNIVERSE AS THE WAVEFUNCTION THEN THE TOTAL ENERGY YIELDS TO BE ZERO.

A geometrical representation can be seen from the above equations by modifying it with X,Y,Z Plane. The equation stated as $\hbar^2\omega^2 - \hbar^2\omega^2$. If we consider the Energy Square as a Z Plane Acting ORTHOGONAL to Antinodes & Nodes such as $(\hbar\omega)^2$ & $-(\hbar\omega)^2$ & considering the Coordinate Axis as X² & Y², then the Resulting Equation stands for...

$$Z = \sqrt{X^2 - Y^2}$$

The corresponding Graph looks like...

The NODES & ANTI-NODES are clearly visible in the Graph Plot along X-Y Plane with Energy as Z Orthogonal to them.

[3]

So, we started with a standing wave 1D with a certain frequency and end up with a standing wave 3D representing the matter-energy dominated universe.

Where the inner Product can be represented as Zero as Z is orthogonal to both X & Y,

Thus,

$$\langle Z^2 | X^2 \rangle = 0$$

$$\langle Z^2 | -Y^2 \rangle = -0$$

Therefore, $\langle Z^2 | X^2 \rangle + \langle Z^2 | -Y^2 \rangle = 0 - 0 = 0$ which again matches with the EQUATION $E^2 = \hbar^2\omega^2 - \hbar^2\omega^2$.

REFERENCES

1. The KLEIN-GORDON Equation stated here is not cited due to lack of reference.
2. Partial differentiation is done online at <https://www.emathhelp.net/calculators/calculus-3/partial-derivative-calculator/>
3. Graph Plotted at www.geogebra.org